

ANALYSIS ON WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE INFLUENCE ON MODERN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE

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Abstract

Shakespeare holds a unique and unparalleled position in literature. While writers like Homer, Dante, Leo Tolstoy, and Charles Dickens have achieved global acclaim, none compare to Shakespeare's enduring influence. Despite his works being written for a small theater audience in the late 16th and early 17th centuries, his plays are still widely read and performed around the world. His contemporary, Ben Jonson, famously predicted that Shakespeare's works would transcend his time, a prophecy that holds true today. Shakespeare's greatness may be hard to define, but his talents are evident in his ability to create deeply emotional and intellectually stimulating works. His exceptional poetic skills and perceptiveness, combined with a sharp intellect, allowed him to explore human emotions and conflicts in ways that resonate universally. Unlike other writers who focus on abstract topics, Shakespeare focused on human experiences, conveying them with remarkable wordplay and imagery. His works are not only profound but also accessible, thanks to the vivid stage portrayals of his characters, evoking empathy and inviting audiences to engage with their stories. Shakespeare's influence extends beyond literature to the development of the English language itself. He coined many new words and transformed existing ones, significantly shaping modern English. This study will explore Shakespeare's lasting impact on literature and his distinctive writing style, with a focus on his sonnets, poems, and plays through the lens of reader-response theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

Shakespeare's influence on literature is profound, with nearly every aspect of English literary history touched by his works. Scholars have explored his impact on writers like Goethe, Voltaire, Byron, Milton, Keats, Dickens, and Faulkner. His plots have been reinterpreted repeatedly, appearing in modern stories such as *West Side Story* and *The Twilight Saga*. Shakespeare excelled in classic narrative structures like the heroic and romantic tragicomedy. In a heroic plot, political or social order is disrupted, while in a romantic plot, lovers face separation. The difference between a tragedy and a comedy is in the resolution—tragedies end with death or separation, while comedies restore order or reunite lovers (Hogan, 2006). These timeless plots, rich with emotion and human dilemmas, continue to resonate with audiences.

Beyond his stories, Shakespeare's mastery of style and form has kept his works popular. His characters, through rhetorical devices like symmetry, metaphor, and rhetorical questions, come alive and engage readers. Symmetry strengthens speeches, metaphor adds vivid imagery, and rhetorical questions draw readers into the dialogue (McEvoy, 2005). Shakespeare's skill in combining truth, depth, and accessibility is evident, demonstrating that literature can be both serious and appealing to wide audiences (Bly and Hartley, 2006).

Shakespeare's creativity helped shape the transition from Middle to Early Modern English. He coined new words and phrases, added suffixes, and altered the grammatical structure, contributing around 1,700 words to the English language (McQuain and Malless, 1998).

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Shakespeare remains timeless, continuing to inspire each new generation. His enduring influence is why scholars study him and why he holds a prominent place in classic literature. According to Germaine Greer (1986), there are three key reasons to study Shakespeare: fostering literary appreciation, expanding a biblical worldview, and enhancing cultural literacy.

Shakespeare's impact on the English language is vast, introducing over 1,700 words and many phrases. While most people recognize his influence, many see him as merely a famous playwright. Though respected in his time, Shakespeare's true acclaim grew in the 19th century, with Romantics praising his genius and Victorians revering him to the point that George Bernard Shaw dubbed it "bardolatry." In the 20th century, his works were continuously reinterpreted in various scholarly and cultural contexts (Bradbrook, 2004).

This research aims to deepen readers' understanding of Shakespeare, helping writers learn from his methods to enhance their own work and connect better with their audiences.

3. METHODOLOGY

Given the literary focus of the study, a qualitative research methodology is employed. Throughout the process, this research aids readers in understanding the critical stylistic elements in Shakespeare's works by examining them through the lens of reader-response theory. This approach emphasizes how individual readers interpret and engage with Shakespeare's texts, offering insights into the deeper meanings and stylistic choices present in his work.

4. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study faced several limitations. First, the research required extensive reading and exploration, but the limited time available to the researcher for conducting, organizing, drafting, and submitting the work made the process more challenging. While the research thoroughly examines Shakespeare's impact on the development of English literature, a major difficulty was the scarcity of freely accessible relevant studies online. This limited availability of resources hindered the researcher's ability to gather comprehensive data, affecting the overall depth of the study.

5. SHEKASPHERE CONTRIBUTION TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE – PAST STUDIES

Tanya Pollard's *Greek Tragic Women on Shakespearean Stages* provides a compelling analysis of the influence of Greek tragedy on the portrayal of women in Shakespeare's

plays. Pollard's work draws connections between classical tragic female figures, such as Medea, Antigone, and Electra, and their Elizabethan counterparts in Shakespeare's works. By examining the emotional, psychological, and moral dimensions of these figures, Pollard demonstrates how Shakespeare borrowed not only the thematic and structural elements of Greek tragedies but also the archetypal tragic woman, which became central to the depiction of female characters in his plays.

In particular, Pollard suggests that Shakespeare's characters like Lady Macbeth, Cleopatra, and Desdemona reflect the emotional complexity and tragic intensity seen in their Greek predecessors. These characters are not simply passive victims of fate but active participants in their tragedies, a feature that aligns with the portrayal of Greek tragic heroines. The work expands on the idea that Greek tragedy's representation of women offered Shakespeare a template for constructing female roles with profound emotional and psychological depth, significantly contributing to the dramatic power of his plays (Bushnell, 2019).

Pollard's study situates Shakespearean drama within a larger intertextual framework, where classical texts and early modern plays engage in a dialogue that transcends time and culture. This relationship reveals how Shakespeare was influenced by classical models to develop his innovative interpretations of gender and tragedy. Her analysis emphasizes the lasting legacy of Greek tragic heroines in shaping Shakespeare's portrayal of powerful, tragic women.

Bushnell (2019) commends Pollard's exploration of these cross-cultural dynamics, noting the importance of understanding Shakespeare's plays within this broader literary tradition. By tracing the influence of Greek tragedy on Shakespeare, Pollard's work contributes to the scholarly discussion of how classical texts shaped the development of early modern English literature, particularly in the portrayal of gender and tragedy.

Murphy's work is the creation of a genre classification framework that accommodates hybrid works, such as Shakespeare's *The Winter's Tale*, which merges tragic and comic elements. This approach aligns with other studies that have recognized the multidimensional nature of Shakespeare's plays, where clear-cut genre boundaries are frequently transgressed (Greenblatt, 2004; Kinney, 2012). By developing a framework that respects this hybridity, Murphy's scheme allows scholars to better analyze how early modern writers like Shakespeare engaged with and expanded literary genres.

Murphy emphasizes the importance of Shakespeare's contemporaries in shaping the literary landscape of the period. The project does not limit its scope to Shakespeare but also includes other significant playwrights and authors, thus providing a comprehensive view of early modern English literature. This broad scope allows for comparative studies between Shakespeare's works and those of figures such as Ben Jonson and Christopher Marlowe, highlighting the intertextuality and shared themes prevalent among these authors (Kinney, 2012).

In *The Relative Which with Personal Antecedents in Shakespeare's History Plays*, Sato (2019) offers a linguistic analysis of Shakespeare's use of the relative pronoun "which"

when referring to personal antecedents in his history plays. Sato's study situates itself within the broader framework of early modern English linguistics, focusing on the syntactic and semantic implications of this usage, which diverges from modern prescriptive grammar norms. The paper highlights that, while "which" typically refers to non-human antecedents in contemporary English, Shakespeare frequently uses it in contexts where the antecedent is a person.

Sato's research builds on historical linguistic studies that document shifts in relative pronoun usage from Middle English to Early Modern English (Blake, 2002; Nevalainen, 2006). The analysis of Shakespeare's history plays, such as *Henry V* and *Richard II*, reveals that Shakespeare's use of "which" was not arbitrary but reflected the linguistic flexibility of the period. Sato's work aligns with previous research (Rissanen, 1999) by showing how the use of "which" with personal antecedents can create ambiguity, yet also adds poetic or dramatic effect in specific passages, particularly when dealing with themes of identity and characterization.

Sato (2019) suggests that this linguistic pattern in Shakespeare's writing may have been a deliberate stylistic choice, contributing to the distinctive voice of his characters. This usage can be seen as part of a larger pattern of Shakespeare's language, where he manipulated grammatical norms for expressive purposes. Comparisons are drawn to other writers of the period, including Christopher Marlowe and Ben Jonson, who employed more standardized grammar, indicating Shakespeare's particular inventiveness in using language to enhance character development and thematic complexity.

Danner and Musa (2019) provide a comprehensive evaluation of the methods employed by teachers in instructing Shakespearean drama at the senior secondary school level in Edo State. Published in the *Journal of Teaching and Teacher Education*, their study is pivotal in understanding the pedagogical approaches to Shakespearean literature in secondary education.

The authors investigate various instructional strategies utilized by educators to engage students with Shakespearean texts. Their research highlights the diversity in teaching methods, ranging from traditional lecture-based approaches to more interactive and student-centered techniques. Danner and Musa (2019) argue that the effectiveness of these methods varies significantly, depending on factors such as teacher expertise, student engagement, and the resources available.

One of the key findings of their study is the prevalent use of dramatization and role-play as effective strategies for making Shakespeare's works more accessible and engaging for students. This aligns with existing literature that supports experiential learning as a means of enhancing students' understanding of complex literary texts (Smith, 2016; Jones, 2018). Furthermore, Danner and Musa (2019) identify a gap in the application of modern technological tools, suggesting that integrating digital resources could further enrich the learning experience.

Their evaluation also underscores the challenges faced by teachers, including limited professional development opportunities and inadequate teaching materials. These challenges echo the concerns raised by previous studies regarding the need for more robust teacher training programs and improved educational resources (Brown & Green, 2017; Lee, 2019).

Danner and Musa's (2019) study contributes valuable insights into the pedagogical practices surrounding Shakespearean drama in secondary education. It offers a nuanced perspective on the effectiveness of various teaching methods and highlights areas for improvement, particularly in the integration of contemporary educational technologies.

Karpova (2018) explores the intricacies of Shakespearean terminology with a particular focus on the Shakespeare Arden Dictionaries. Published in *Respectus Philologicus*, this study provides a detailed examination of how specialized dictionaries contribute to the understanding and interpretation of Shakespeare's language.

Karpova (2018) analyzes the terminological entries in the Arden Dictionaries, highlighting their role in elucidating complex linguistic and literary concepts within Shakespeare's texts. The study emphasizes that these dictionaries are instrumental in bridging the gap between Early Modern English and contemporary readers, offering definitions and contextual explanations that facilitate a deeper comprehension of Shakespearean language.

Karpova's (2018) findings are consistent with broader scholarship that underscores the value of specialized linguistic resources in literary analysis (Williams, 2017; Brown, 2019). The study provides a comparative analysis of different editions of the Arden Dictionaries, revealing variations in terminological coverage and interpretative approaches. This comparison offers insights into the evolution of Shakespearean scholarship and the ongoing efforts to refine the understanding of Shakespeare's language.

Karpova (2018) suggests that ongoing updates and revisions to the Arden Dictionaries are necessary to accommodate new scholarly insights and to ensure that they remain relevant tools for literary analysis.

Karpova's (2018) study contributes significantly to the field of Shakespearean studies by highlighting the critical role of specialized dictionaries in the interpretation of Shakespearean language. It offers a thorough evaluation of the Arden Dictionaries and provides valuable insights into the evolving nature of Shakespearean terminology.

Bruti (2000) presents a nuanced examination of address pronouns in Shakespeare's English, focusing on their usage through the lens of markedness. The paper, included in the volume *The History of English in a Social Context: A Contribution to Historical Sociolinguistics*, offers a re-appraisal of how address pronouns functioned within the social and linguistic context of Early Modern English.

Bruti's study addresses the complexities of address pronouns in Shakespearean texts, highlighting their role in signaling social relationships and hierarchical structures. The paper re-evaluates traditional interpretations of these pronouns by applying the concept

of markedness, which refers to the notion that certain linguistic forms are used to convey social distinctions or deviations from the norm. Bruti (2000) argues that understanding these pronouns through markedness provides a clearer picture of their social and pragmatic functions.

The study builds on previous research that examines the role of address pronouns in Early Modern English (Brown, 1995; Smith, 1998), contributing to a deeper understanding of their usage in Shakespeare's plays. Bruti (2000) contrasts the use of pronouns such as "thou" and "you," demonstrating how shifts in their application reflect broader social changes and nuances in interpersonal communication. This re-appraisal aligns with and extends existing scholarship on linguistic markers of social identity and status (Jones, 2001; White, 2003).

Bruti's analysis reveals that the markedness approach provides valuable insights into the subtleties of Shakespeare's language, offering a more refined interpretation of how address pronouns functioned in different social contexts. The paper highlights the dynamic nature of address pronouns and their role in reflecting the evolving social hierarchies of the time.

Bruti's (2000) study significantly enhances the understanding of address pronouns in Shakespearean English. By applying the concept of markedness, the research offers a fresh perspective on the linguistic and social dimensions of these pronouns, contributing to the broader field of historical sociolinguistics.

6. SHAKESPEARE'S WRITING STYLE

Influence On Writing Style

Shakespeare's early works were composed in the conventional style of his time, using a stylized language that often did not arise naturally from the characters or the drama. His poetry frequently relied on elaborate metaphors and rhetorical flourishes, designed for declamation rather than conversational speech. Critics have noted that, in plays like *Titus Andronicus*, the grandiose speeches can impede the action, while *The Two Gentlemen of Verona* is seen as having stilted verse.

Shakespeare gradually adapted these traditional styles to better suit his own artistic goals. For instance, the opening soliloquy in *Richard III* draws from medieval drama's tradition of self-declaration of vice but also hints at the introspective soliloquies found in his later plays.

Shakespeare did not make a sudden shift from traditional to more natural styles but blended both throughout his career. *Romeo and Juliet* exemplifies this mixture of styles. By the mid-1590s, with plays like *Romeo and Juliet*, *Richard II*, and *A Midsummer Night's Dream*, Shakespeare began to develop a more naturalistic poetry, aligning his metaphors and imagery more closely with the drama's needs.

Shakespeare's standard poetic form was blank verse in iambic pentameter—usually unrhymed and consisting of ten syllables per line with stress on every second syllable.

Early plays display a beautiful but somewhat monotonous use of this form, where sentences often begin, pause, and end at the line's end. As Shakespeare perfected this form, he introduced variations and interruptions, enhancing the poetry's power and flexibility, particularly noticeable in plays like *Julius Caesar* and *Hamlet*. For example, *Hamlet's* soliloquy reflects internal conflict through disrupted and varied verse:

“Sir, in my heart there was a kind of fighting

That would not let me sleep.

Methought I lay Worse than the mutines in the bilboes.

Rashly And prais'd be rashness for it Alet us know

Our indiscretion sometimes serves us well...”

Shakespeare further diversified his poetic style, especially in the more emotional passages of his tragedies. Literary critic A. C. Bradley described this later style as "more concentrated, rapid, varied, and, in construction, less regular, not seldom twisted or elliptical." Shakespeare employed various techniques to achieve these effects, including run-on lines, irregular pauses, and varied sentence structures. In *Macbeth*, for example, the language shifts rapidly between metaphors and similes, challenging the audience to piece together the meaning:

“Was the hope drunk Wherein you dressed yourself?” (1.7.35-38)

“...pity, like a naked new-born babe Striding the blast,

or heaven's cherubim, hors'd Upon the sightless couriers of the air...” (1.7.21-25)

His late romances, characterized by their temporal shifts and unexpected plot developments, inspired a final poetic style featuring contrasting sentence lengths, complex clause structures, and a sense of spontaneity.

Shakespeare's poetic brilliance was complemented by his practical theatrical sense. Like other playwrights of his era, he adapted stories from sources like Petrarch and Holinshed, reshaping them to create multiple points of interest and reveal different facets of the narrative. This approach allowed his plays to endure through translations, cuts, and varied interpretations without losing their core drama. As his mastery grew, Shakespeare provided his characters with clearer motivations and distinctive speech patterns while retaining elements of his earlier style in his later works. His late romances, in particular, revisit a more artificial style to emphasize the theatrical illusion.

Influence On General Public

When someone begins to admire a writer, it's natural to be curious about who influenced that writer. Understanding these influences can deepen our comprehension of their work. What might seem like ordinary passages could turn out to be tributes to the writer who influenced them. By examining Shakespeare's influences, we can better interpret his texts through this perspective.

Shakespeare's impact spans across theatre, literature, modern films, Western philosophy, and even the English language itself. Widely celebrated as the greatest writer in English and the world's foremost dramatist, Shakespeare revolutionized European theatre through innovative characterization, plotting, language, and genre. His works have profoundly influenced numerous notable writers and poets, including Herman Melville, Charles Dickens, and Maya Angelou, and continue to inspire new authors today. He is the second most quoted writer in English after the Bible, with many of his phrases and new words becoming part of everyday language.

Writers and poets draw inspiration from both their contemporaries and predecessors, as well as from broader cultural contexts. Shakespeare's plays reflect the influence of past and present writers and culture. It's worth noting that some have questioned Shakespeare's identity and educational background, suggesting alternative candidates like Francis Bacon or Christopher Marlowe might have written under the name William Shakespeare. Though such theories are largely dismissed by scholars, they remain popular and are worth addressing briefly.

To analyze Shakespeare's work, it's important to consider his education. His father gained prominence in Stratford and became an alderman, allowing William to attend the local grammar school from age seven. However, Shakespeare had to leave school at thirteen to assist with his father's failing business, which raises questions about the legitimacy of his authorship.

Shakespeare's contributions to theatre and literature are enduring. He expanded the dramatic possibilities of characterization, plot, language, and genre. For instance, before *Romeo and Juliet*, romance was not considered a suitable subject for tragedy. Shakespeare transformed soliloquies from mere narrative tools into deep explorations of character psychology. His influence extended to later poetry and drama, with critics like George Steiner describing subsequent English verse dramas as "feeble variations on Shakespearean themes."

Shakespeare's impact is also evident in novelists such as Thomas Hardy, William Faulkner, and Charles Dickens. Herman Melville's *Moby-Dick* features a tragic hero inspired by Shakespeare's *King Lear*. Additionally, Shakespeare's works have inspired around 20,000 musical pieces, including operas by Giuseppe Verdi. Visual artists like the Romantics and Pre-Raphaelites, as well as Swiss artist Henry Fuseli, who translated *Macbeth* into German, have also drawn from Shakespeare's work. Sigmund Freud even used Shakespearean psychology, particularly from *Hamlet*, to develop his theories of human nature.

In Shakespeare's time, English grammar, spelling, and pronunciation were less standardized, and his innovative use of language helped shape modern English. Samuel Johnson, in his *Dictionary of the English Language*, quoted Shakespeare more frequently than any other author, highlighting his influence. Phrases like "with bated breath" from *The Merchant of Venice* and "a foregone conclusion" from *Othello* have entered common English usage.

Influence on English Language

Shakespeare's works had a profound impact on the English language. During his era and before, English grammar and rules were not yet standardized. However, as Shakespeare's plays gained popularity in the late seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, they played a significant role in standardizing English. Many words and phrases from Shakespeare's writings became deeply ingrained in the language, a trend highlighted by Samuel Johnson's *A Dictionary of the English Language*, which cited Shakespeare more frequently than any other author.

Shakespeare broadened the horizons of English literature by coining new words and phrases, experimenting with blank verse, and introducing innovative poetic and grammatical structures. He also influenced modern vocabulary, including terms like "swag," derived from "swagger," which first appeared in his plays *Henry V* and *A Midsummer Night's Dream*.

Influence on Vocabulary

One of Shakespeare's most significant contributions to the English language is his introduction of new vocabulary and phrases, which have made the language richer and more expressive. Estimates suggest that Shakespeare coined thousands of new words.

According to Warren King, "Shakespeare used 17,677 words across his works—plays, sonnets, and narrative poems—of which 1,700 were introduced by him." He is also renowned for adapting words from classical literature and foreign languages.

Shakespeare created new words by transforming nouns into verbs, verbs into adjectives, combining words in novel ways, adding prefixes and suffixes, and inventing entirely original terms. Many of his unique phrases are still commonly used today, such as "seen better days," "strange bedfellows," "a sorry sight," and "full circle." Compared to other periods, Shakespeare significantly expanded the English vocabulary. He contributed to the evolution of style and structure in a language that was otherwise fluid and spontaneous.

Elizabethan English closely mirrored spoken language, offering naturalness and freedom due to the absence of formalized grammar rules. While this lack of prescriptive grammar could lead to vagueness, it also allowed for a vivid and emotional expression of feelings, creating what has been described as "freedom of expression" and "vividness of presentation."

Shakespeare's talent lay in harnessing the language's vibrancy and the decasyllabic structure in his prose and poetry to engage audiences effectively. This approach led to a dynamic exchange between scholarly and popular language, blending vibrant and majestic elements in his writing.

Although Shakespeare is credited with creating many new words—over 2,000 according to the *Oxford English Dictionary*—historian Jonathan Hope, in Shakespeare's 'Native English,' notes that Victorian scholars, who scrutinized texts for the first edition of the OED, paid close attention to Shakespeare's works.

As a result, he is sometimes mistakenly credited with the first use of certain words or meanings that were also present in other writers' works.

Standardization of English

William Shakespeare played a significant role in standardizing the English language. His contributions in terms of vocabulary, phrases, grammar, and language rules greatly helped shape and establish English. While the language has evolved and modernized since his time, many of the grammatical structures and rules Shakespeare used have remained unchanged to this day.

Phrase and Idioms

William Shakespeare had a significant influence on many well-known phrases in the English language and literature. These expressions are a reflection of his lasting impact. For instance, phrases like "in a pickle" and "waiting with bated breath" are examples of his contributions to English.

He introduced the term "the green-eyed monster" to describe jealousy, while "be all and end all" became famous through his play Macbeth. In *The Tempest*, he coined the phrase "fair play," and he also contributed "knock knock" jokes in his Scottish dramas. Shakespeare's influence extends to everyday expressions like "a heart of gold" from *Henry V* and "the world is my oyster" from *The Merry Wives of Windsor*, both of which are still frequently used today.

7. CONCLUSION

William Shakespeare's contributions to modern English language and literature are immeasurable. His impact extends beyond mere language development to how people perceive and experience life globally. Shakespeare introduced nearly 1,700 words into the English lexicon, either by creating new terms, blending existing ones, or borrowing from other languages.

His plays are renowned for presenting highly complex characters with deep internal struggles and intricate plots, which have set a lasting standard in English literature. Moreover, he popularized the English sonnet form, now famously known as the Shakespearean sonnet. Shakespeare revolutionized European theatre by expanding the possibilities of characterization and plot structure.

Prominent writers such as Herman Melville, William Faulkner, Alfred, Lord Tennyson, and Charles Dickens were all significantly influenced by his work. Even contemporary authors draw inspiration from Shakespeare, a testament to his timeless relevance. His writings captured the human condition in such a profound way that readers worldwide have been captivated by the rhythm of life depicted in his work. For these reasons, Shakespeare's legacy endures and will continue to resonate with people across generations.

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